
ALIENATION, SECLUSION, AND DEGRADATION OF CHARACTERS IN ELIOT'S THE FAMILY REUNION

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Abstract:

Leadership may be a vital issue in any organization. The nature of academic administration modified so fast during the early twentieth the first twentieth century. A healthy Organization is one that not solely survives this atmosphere however, additionally continues to grow and prosper over the future for a long time. Leadership style emerges out of the interaction of issues for tasks and relationships. Leadership is needed in each school and at each level of management, the success or failure of a faculty depends on the kind of leadership approach is being practiced at the amount of top management. Leadership is often outlined by the traits, qualities, and behaviors of a leader. The study of leadership has spanned across cultures, decades, and theoretical beliefs.

Leaders were born, not made, and therefore the key to success was merely in distinguishing those societies that were born to be good leaders. Though abundant analysis was done to advert the traits, no clear answer was found with respect to what traits systematically were related to nice leadership. Goal accomplishment is a crucial issue within the leadership method. The leader influences its members within the accomplishment of goals by following specific directions. Therefore, leadership involves directional a group of lecturers toward some upshot or accomplishing school objectives.

Keywords: *Leader, Principals, dynamic leader, Leadership stycler.*

Introduction:

According to Halpin (1957) ⁶ "The principal was an honest leader, approachable likewise as broad-minded, able to bring out the simplest in others and tapped their strength to reinforce the operation of the school". Head of the college with unhealthy leader behavior not solely tends to incapacitate himself for the performance of his multifaceted duties in schools however additionally creates difficulties and issues for his subordinates.

Academic excellence is barely one version of good school and only one contributor to the understanding of what good schools are and the way they are available into being.

In today's competitive environment, school system faces new challenges regarding the development of organizational commitment. "Most successful school leaders will tell you. that getting the culture right and paying attention to how parents, teachers, and students define and experience meaning are two widely accepted rules for creating effective schools. We still have to worry about standards,

the curriculum, teacher development, tests, resources, and the creation of appropriate management designs that help get things done. But these concerns: will not matter much unless the right culture is in place and unless parents, teachers, and students interact with the school in meaningful ways."

T.J. Sergiovanni (1992)

The new leader contains a well-balanced intellect (IQ), mind (EQ), and multi-disciplinary (holistic) perspective. He listens a lot of and speaks less, observes a lot of and concludes less, uses 'we' quite 'I', and says 'let's go' a lot of typically than 'go. He takes quite his share of the blame and fewer than his share of the credit. He is open and however decisive, focuses on human processes instead of solely on end-results, and is a lot of an educator and fewer of a boss.

A leader by definition, intention, and action can't be a doubter. Gandhi whereas in his Sevagram Ashram at Wardha (Maharashtra) on day, February 2, 1946, determined that "only he are often a leader who never loses hope." A dynamic leader achieves a competitive advantage for his organization by inspiring and empowering the people to form the simplest contribution and serving to them to continue in a company not withstanding perks and emoluments might not be best for them. Excluding an honest regular payment, lack of labor challenge and galvanizing leadership, being the most reasons for a faculty to retain an honest teacher in a very public setup. School Academic Performance will, deliberately and specifically, target schools and has been unapologetically directed at explaining what goes on inside the college. Its strength and unique contribution to the understanding of schools is additionally its most singular weakness, however.

The requirement to manage the variables like home background needs that these items are factored out, therefore risking the loss of knowledge on the foremost vital area for the improvement of learning the dynamic relationship between what pupils rouse school and what they subtract from college (MacBeath, 1995)¹¹. The popularity of a school depends on however it's projected to the outside world whereas academic excellence and growth altogether fields are influenced by internal factors. All these can have a direct concerning Academic performance. During this context, it's thought necessary to research however way the Leadership style of the Principal or Head master of the college has an effect on Students Academic Performances. Management analysis literature indicates that leadership method 'L' is 'a perform of leader 'I' followers/group 'f' and scenario variables' i.e., $L = (1, f, s)$ (Hersey and Blanchard, 1991). A outline of what's better-known and understood concerning leadership is vital to precede more analysis on the term leadership.

The present study has variable quantity as Leadership Style that consists of six dimensions: Assertive Administration (D1), Constructional Leadership (D2). Assumption of Responsibility (D3), Personal Vision. (D4), call Maldng (D5), and Standard Relationship Style (D6)

The main plan of the current study is however the dimensions of Leadership. (Style will have the impact of Academic Performances).

Defining Leadership:

According to Luthans (2008), "leadership has been defined in a number of ways." A leader can be seen as a person who is appointed, elected or formally chosen to direct and coordinate the work of others in a group. (Arnold & Randall, 2010).

Objectives of the Present Study:

The following are the objectives of the study. •

- I. To find out the main leadership styles used by school Principals for the Academic Performances of the schools.
- II. To study the types of leadership for improvement in the organization.
- III. To study the dimensions of the leadership for achieving the success of school

Need and Importance of the Study:

What makes an organization successful? Leadership abilities are crucial skills. The headmaster's role is to serve as a democratic leader than to be a dictator or autocratic giver of orders.. The academic excellence of schools principally depends on the Leadership style of the heads of the schools. The findings of this study would facilitate to boost the educational standards of various kinds of schools. Leaders create a permanent imprint on their Organizations each by what they are doing and the way they act. Nobody is accepted by others as their leader, unless he has made some efforts, but tentative, to act in such some way on be perceived as a possible leader. The purpose of this study was to explore the leadership styles for the Principals to improve the effectiveness of the school.

Research Methodology:

The secondary data have been collected from different sources like journals, research reports and books. Descriptive research describes the state of affairs as it exists at the present moment, in reality for everyone to perceive. The present study has been planned as a descriptive research. It aims at investigating Leadership Style. The dimensions of leadership. So, the secondary data is used from different research papers, thesis, & articles.

Statement of the Problem:

Leadership effectiveness of Principals is principally judged by the students' educational performance. Academic issues, which could embrace problems like learning difficulties or disabilities, performance, lack of attention from teachers, and bullying. It will have an effect on diversity of scholars throughout their academic careers, from primary school to the college..

Most schools expertise lack of delegation of duties, effective information direction to the supervisors and implementation as a result of the headmaster's are never at school to implement it or are fully busy with alternative administrative duties except teaching, as he is totally responsible for the academic performance in a school.

Review of Related Literature:

According to Osland et al. (2007), the primary task of this new style of leader is to make an structure foundation of purpose, vision, and core values by that the societies can live. The leader takes on the mantle of teacher, mentor, and steward who fifteen empower people to make new mental models of reality.

Many leaders have a magnetic result on people, typically observed as having personal charisma. In finding out this elusive quality in terms of behavior, social scientists found that charisma people are a lot of animated than others; they smile a lot of, speak quicker, pronounce words a lot of clearly,

and move their heads and bodies a lot of often; in different words, they exude energy and quality (Kouzes & Posner, 2007)⁸.

Leithwood et al. (2008)⁹ wrote that school leaders exhibit a couple of common personal traits, apart from charisma, that specify a lot of their effectiveness. Those traits embrace being (a) broad-minded and willing to be told from others; (b) flexible instead of dogmatic; (c) persistent, particularly in pursuit of high expectations and accomplishment for all; (d) resilient; and (e) optimistic.

Clawson (2009) wrote concerning Level three leadership. Level three leaders manage energy first in themselves so in those around them. These leaders behave at three levels: (a) their visible behavior, (b) their conscious thought, and (c) their values, assumptions, beliefs, and expectations concerning the manner the globe either is or ought to be (Clawson, 2009)¹¹.

Leadership is comparable to management; however it's additionally completely different. Northouse (2010) found that management's perform is to produce order and consistency to organizations, whereas leadership's perform is to supply modification and movement. Smart leaders perceive the work that must be done and may relate to the people that facilitate them do the duty (Northouse, 2010)¹².

Leadership Designs - Vital Factors:

The study of Jennings (1961) was to spot the link between specific principal Leadership designs and also the effectiveness of urban elementary colleges. Leadership designs as being benevolent-authoritarian to informatory. The extent of Leadership designs and. suggests that for high-achieving schools understood that high-achieving colleges employees expected and received a lot of from their students, staff, and community because it associated with their commitment to tutorial excellence.

1 Charismatic Leadership having its origins in Greek civilization, charisma springs from ingrained personal traits, such as over-reaching ambition, unshakeable self-confidence, and the penchant for setting a personal example. The charismatic leader uses •• more of natural behavior and less of technique. He is also a superb debater, a potent persuader, a technical expert, and a catalyst of changes spanning his followers' attitudes and emotions.

2 Transactional Leadership A balanced approach, which suits actions to the situation and the maturity of followers, this style of leadership combines an orientation towards results and a focus on people to the precise degree necessary in a particular situation. The transactional leader does not focus on inspiration at the expense of practical guidance, and clarifies the roles and tasks required of followers.

3 Transformational Leadership: the elemental task is to metamorphose the values, beliefs, and desires of followers. The essence of this manner of leadership~ lies in simplifying vital problems through the use of symbols and paying personal attention to each individual follower. Change-agent learns as he coaches and may deal with confidence with complexness. Transformational leadership enhances the expansion of followers, exalting them to suppose in which they're not acquainted with thinking, motivating them to accomplish on the far side what they felt was

attainable, and inspiring them to try to thus by keeping in mind the values and high ethical standards that guide their performance.

- 4 Attributed Leadership:** The perception of followers, and not the behavior. or characteristics of leaders, explains this manner of leadership. Results-spectacular success or abysmal failures area unit attributed by people to specific characteristics of the one who is accountable. The attributed leader sometimes demonstrates high intelligence, associate outgoing temperament, robust verbal skills, aggressiveness, understanding, and industriousness.
- 5. Distributed leadership style:.** Another leadership vogue mentioned within the literature is distributed leadership. Wright (2008) supported distributed leadership, during which Principals share the leadership with lecturers and employees in order that the principal isn't needed to be the only real skilled altogether areas of student accomplishment.
- 6. Authentic leadership style:** Authentic leadership vogue. one amongst the latest areas of leadership analysis is authentic leadership caused by economic concern and uncertainty. People area unit desperate for the leadership they will trust and for leaders who are ethical and honest.
- 7. Servant leadership style:** Authentic leadership is very closely aligned to servant leadership. The term servant leadership is attributed to Robert Greenleaf (1991)³ Heifetz, who believed that people will follow leaders who serve them first and then lead them to higher goals through clear vision and encouragement. It is the leader's vision, belief, and trust in others that can make a vision happen. In his research on the behaviors of caring leaders, Greenleaf found that they (a) love life, (b) have a good sense of humor, (c) lead with love for others, (d) empower others to do their jobs, (e) give them opportunities for growth, (f) are master communicators and listeners, and (g) never give up on their vision.
- 8. Adaptive leadership style:** The normal read of leadership has been displaced in recent years by a refined social modification during which people and establishments that lead don't seem to be expected to grasp all the answers. This approach is thought as adaptive leadership during which leadership is viewed as associate activity instead of a proper position or personal characteristic. Rather than holding all the facility, adaptive leaders produce conditions through those stakeholders take responsibility for effort bit issues (Heifetz et al., 2004) 4.

Recommendations:

One of the hallmarks of leadership is that the ability to get over and learn from a failure or misjudgment. Leaders awaken in their followers a way of upper potential. All potential leaders square measure born with bound qualities. They become leaders solely by formation their craft within the hearth of challenge and competition. Leaders initiate changes that let Organizations to adapt to inevitable challenges from the surroundings and to evolve into the next state. Leadership can't be educated by exposure to convenient tutorial modules, despite the claims of the many leadership gurus. Lecturers understand the vision depends greatly on college leaders agency will generate enthusiasm and commitment and encourage, care, respect, support, and involve lecturers in decision-making.

The quality of the student's performance is one among the most factors, that makes a faculty a lot of well-liked. The principal and also the lecturers got to oft monitor the students' progress. Teacher management and teacher leadership additionally might contribute to high school effectiveness. A dynamical world demands a replacement leadership vogue action social group impact and commitment to the commonweal. The leadership of school Principals could be a decisive consider school effectiveness, second solely to the role of a student's schoolroom teacher (Leithwood et al., 2008). To achieve success, Principals have continually had to manage the stress of a variety of stakeholders; but, within the twenty first century, these stakeholders have a lot of power to influence and intervene (Day, 2007) ² Day, C.

Findings of this Study:

The major findings of this study proven that the Leadership kind of the Principal of the varsity is extremely a lot of associated with the tutorial Performance of the scholars. coaching ought to be conducted by extremely capable persons permanently leadership for Principals, with sensible Leadership vogue and well old have additionally to be invited to steer the cluster of Principals during this coaching, to share the experiences of getting made sensible results. Heads of colleges ought to keep them updated by learning all the electronic equipment techniques of teaching with an honest Leadership vogue. In step with Halpin (1957) 6. "the principal was an honest leader, approachable yet as broad-minded, ready to bring out the simplest in others and a broach their strength to reinforce the operation of the school". The findings from this study show that the colleges that cannot provide sensible performance in lecturers have to be compelled to be given special care and necessary remedial measures like giving leadership coaching for the Principals.

Conclusion of this Study:

Good leadership depends totally on what leaders do, not on their qualities or vogue. As organizations and also the world become a lot of complicated and unpredictable, all the leaders in organizations should be inspired to become a lot of self-managing and to assume bigger personal authority. To market effective principal leadership development, one ought to have an understanding of these aspects of leadership and what the analysis shows to be the foremost effective leadership among Principals. Organizations that encourage the expansion of their workers increase their personal mastery.

Effective leadership is important to the no-hit functioning of nearly any organization, not simply faculties. For hundreds of years, students have tried to grasp what ends up in success in leadership. To the current day, effective leadership continues to elude people and organizations. Leadership consultants disagree greatly on that precise leadership theories, styles, traits, behaviors, or approaches garner the foremost positive results.

It is beyond any doubt clear that differing types of situations necessitate differing types of behavior. There's no guarantee that anyone leadership behavior can invariably be effective. However it ought to be understood that any leadership behavior used by the leader whereas administering the affairs of his workplace is probably going to possess a control on school performance, be it positive or negative. Leaders do not operate in isolation; they work with individuals.

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